

COMPETENCE REQUIREMENTS FOR FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE COMMONWEALTH STATE EDUCATION STANDARDS

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Abstract. *The content of the requirements for the competence of future pedagogues is mentioned in the State educational standards for the training of bachelors in the field of pedagogy from the countries of the Commonwealth of Nations, such as Russia and Belarus.*

Keywords: *physics, competence approach, basic competences, science-related competences, creative competence, general cultural competence, general professional competence, professional competence, special competence.*

In the current conditions, where the priorities and values of our society are changing, new demands are placed on the education system. This requirement is the main goal of the school - forming a socially flexible creative person.

In such conditions, the tasks of the teacher should not be limited to giving the student only a certain amount of knowledge and skills, but should be the formation of a new way of thinking in the young generation that encourages them to behave in accordance with the new conditions. The effectiveness of the teacher's work today should be evaluated whether they prepare students for independent creative activity or not.

Accordingly, it determines the search for new approaches and technologies in the training of future teachers in order to qualitatively update the requirements for the training of future teachers. From this, there is a need to activate scientific-research works both in the field of teacher training and in the direction of teaching separate academic subjects.

Naturally, all this also applies to physics, which is taught as a general education subject and where scientific research is carried out. In school courses, students are taught not only the standard amount of knowledge necessary for each person, but also the achievements of the human mind in solving problems on the way to learning the world, discovering its laws and is obliged to provide classic examples of techniques and methods of creative activity for mastering.

Studying physics at school at the level of modern requirements depends primarily on high-level theoretical, methodological, psychological, pedagogical and scientific training of teachers.

From the point of view of the competence approach, the teacher should know what general, subject-specific and basic competences should be formed in the process of teaching his academic subject, and should have the competence to form them:

- the teacher's knowledge of the main types of planning educational activities, modern teaching technologies, constructive and technological competence related to the design and implementation of various types of educational activities;

- operational and pedagogical competence related to the knowledge and mastery of specific technologies, methods and methods of teaching, which ensures that the teaching process is carried

out at a high professional and pedagogical level in order to achieve high-quality education by the teacher;

- reflexive-pedagogical competence related to the teacher's ability to critically evaluate the process and results of his pedagogical activity, to make necessary corrections;

- qualitative competence related to the development and practical application of the most objective, optimal means of measuring the educational achievements of the teacher's students. This competence should be aimed at training, development, motivation, correction and other functions, not just supervision;

- creative competence, related to creative processes in pedagogical activity, often implemented at an intuitive level.

The creative competence of a teacher is his ability to know the laws of creative pedagogical activity, to design innovative forms of teaching and upbringing, to measure their effectiveness, to make necessary changes, to make pedagogical interpretation of the achieved results, to give lectures, presentations, to participate in the exchange of experience, etc. implies.

Let's see how the above is put into practice in the educational system. For this, the requirements for the competence of future pedagogues in the State educational standards for training bachelors in the field of pedagogy from the countries of the Commonwealth of Nations, such as Russia and Belarus, were studied.

By order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated December 4, 2015 No. 1426 "44.03.01 Federal state educational standard of higher education in the direction of Pedagogical education (bachelor's level)" was approved. Its 4.3.

The types of professional activities of the graduates who mastered the bachelor's program are listed in the paragraph. According to it, the types of activities:

- pedagogical;

- designing;

- research;

- cultural and educational.

5.1 of the standards. according to the paragraph, the graduates who mastered the bachelor's program should have developed general cultural, general professional and professional competences.

5.2. A graduate of a bachelor's program must have 9 universal competencies:

- the ability to use the foundations of philosophical and social-humanitarian knowledge to form a scientific outlook;

- the ability to analyze the main stages and laws of historical development in order to form a patriotic and civic position;

- the ability to use natural science and mathematical knowledge to get the right direction in the modern information space;

- the ability to communicate orally and in writing in Russian and foreign languages to establish interpersonal and intercultural relations;

- ability to work in a team, to be tolerant of social, cultural and personal differences;

- the ability to receive independent education and organize one's work;

- the ability to use basic legal knowledge in various fields of activity;

- the ability to maintain a level of physical fitness that ensures full activity;

- the ability to use first aid techniques and protective methods in emergency situations.

5.3. A graduate of a bachelor's program should have 6 general professional competencies:

- readiness to understand the social importance of his future profession and to have motivation to engage in professional activities;
- the ability to teach, educate and develop students taking into account their social, age, psychophysical and individual characteristics, including special educational needs;
- willingness to provide psychological and pedagogical support to the educational process;
- readiness for professional activity in accordance with the regulatory and legal documents of the field of education;
- to have the basics of professional ethics and speech culture;
- readiness to ensure protection of life and health of learners.

5.4. A graduate who has mastered a bachelor's program must have professional competencies in the following areas corresponding to the type (types) of professional activity: pedagogical activity; design activities; research activities and cultural and educational activities. Total professional competencies are 14.

Pedagogical activities:

- readiness to implement educational programs in the subject in accordance with the requirements of educational standards;
- the ability to use modern methods and technologies of training and diagnosis;
- students' ability to solve problems of educational and spiritual and moral development in educational and extracurricular activities;
- the ability to achieve personal, metasubject and science-related results from the opportunities of the educational environment and to ensure the quality of the educational process with the help of the taught subject;
- the ability to provide pedagogical support for students' socialization and professional self-awareness;
- readiness to communicate with the participants of the educational process;
- the ability to organize students' cooperation, maintain students' activity and initiative, independence, and develop their creative abilities.

On design activities:

- the ability to design educational programs;
- the ability to design individual educational courses for learners;
- the ability to design the directions of his professional growth and personal development.

On research activities:

- readiness to use systematic theoretical and practical knowledge in conducting research to identify problems in the field of education and find their solution;
- the ability of learners to manage educational and research activities.

On cultural and educational activities:

- the ability to identify and form the cultural needs of various social groups;
- the ability to develop and implement cultural and educational programs.

Thus, to obtain a bachelor's degree, a graduate must have 29 types of competence.

The terms "competence" and "competence" are also defined in the approved state educational standards for the preparation of bachelors in the Republic of Belarus.

competence - the ability to apply knowledge and skills to achieve specified results (СТБ ИСО 9000-2015);

competence - knowledge, skills, experience and personal qualities necessary for solving theoretical and practical problems.

Graduates of a higher educational institution must have 2 types of competencies:

6.1 Universal Competencies

6.2. Professional background and special competencies.

The composition of universal competencies is common for all specialists graduating from a higher educational institution. There are 7 of them.

To know the laws of historical development and formation of state and public institutions of the Belarusian ethnos together with European civilization.

To acquire a culture of thinking, to perceive and analyze philosophical problems, to implement psychological and pedagogical knowledge in social and professional activities.

To be able to analyze socially important events, events and processes, to be able to use economic and social information in professional activities, to be able to show entrepreneurial initiative.

To understand the specific aspects of the formation and existence of the political system, the specific features of the state ideology, to be able to analyze the socio-political events of the country and the world, to acquire the skills of political culture.

To acquire basic skills of oral and written communication in a foreign language in order to solve career-oriented tasks, interpersonal and intercultural interaction issues.

To acquire the skills of effective speech communication in Belarusian to successfully solve problems in the professional and socio-cultural sphere.

Having the ability to maintain health.

The number and content of the professional base and special competencies are created taking into account the specific characteristics of the specialty.

In the approved standards for the training of higher pedagogic personnel in the countries of the Commonwealth of Nations and Uzbekistan, different requirements are set for the competence of future pedagogues. These requirements are of a general nature and require the need to develop a set of special competencies directly related to the profession.

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